

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Organizational innovation and ports logistiques: The case of Agadir port

Meryem Serghini*¹

¹Enseignant-chercheur à la Faculté des Sciences Juridiques, Économiques et Sociales, Université Ibn Zohr- Laboratoire LERAG - AGADIR MAROCO

Correspondence

Biruk Befkadu, Margaret E. Adamek
Corresponding Author:

me.serghini@uiz.ac.ma

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to study the contribution of organizational innovation to the achievement of the logistical performance of the port of Agadir. The results of this research highlight three areas of innovative organizational practices: structure, IS, and Human Resources. The port of Agadir has an interest in adopting management practices. This fact is observed in our qualitative study where the significant impact of organizational innovation on the logistics performance of the port is positive. The mobilization of Network theory recognizes that the managerial approach is a strategic tool for the adoption of innovative organizational practices and not as a source of costs (Michel Callon and Bruno Latour (2016)).

Keywords: Port logistics; organizational innovation; performance; structure; IS

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1.Introduction

In recent years, markets have significantly evolved due to the spatial separation of production centers, consumption centers at the global level. As a result, organizations are constantly looking for strategies that would give them one or more competitive advantages (Serghini 2018). The economic globalization which refers to the integration of operations and markets in an economic area without borders (Azizi Ismail, N. (2008)) and advances in information and communication technologies (Hanna, 2010); is a central environmental force faced by organizations (MAGALA, M. and SAMMONS, A., (2008)).

In such a context, organizations are faced with a challenge to master the different aspects of performance in all phases of their supply chains; a challenge to develop their products without ignoring the quality of their services, to ensure that the resources and means invested in current production remain profitable to meet the needs of their future productions (Tidd J. and Bessant J. (2009)). For this, and given the evolution of the markets, it is not obvious that the acquisition

of technological goods is sufficient to accomplish the tasks of steering and evaluating the performance of the supply chain, conditioned by the nature and diversity of flows which makes these tasks more difficult (serghini 2019; Rojo, A., Stevenson, M., Lloréns Montes, F. J., & Perez-Arostegui, M. N. (2018).

The port supply chain is a very sensitive link within a global logistics chain. Indeed, the port and maritime domain is subject to constraints related to time, cost, and quality. Port functions are changing to serve as an economic catalyst and be centrally positioned to support industries engaged in international trade. Issues of economic stability and corporate responsibility shed new sense on port operations (Wang, N., Liang, H., Zhong, W., Xue, Y., & Xiao, J. (2012). More, growing environmental awareness is stimulating ports to improve their operational viability by considering the expectations of port stakeholders (Wang, N., Liang, H., Zhong, W., Xue, Y., & Xiao, J. (2012); serghini, (2021)).

To meet the current and future needs of ports and their stakeholders, ports must balance land,